

5. Distortion of flag leaves and incomplete emergence of panicles are symptoms of ragged stunt disease.

6. Excessive panicles of infected plants at later growth stages are another symptom of ragged stunt.

be observed in the early regenerated growth; other symptoms appear at booting stage.

So far, studies of ragged stunt transmission through seeds and soil and by mechanical means have yielded no positive results, but the disease can be transmitted by the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*. The causal agent-vector interaction will probably be categorized in the persistent group. Although biotypes 1, 2, and 3 of the brown planthopper differ in their ability to attack rice varieties, no significant difference has been found in their ability to transmit ragged stunt.

The nature of the causal agent of the ragged stunt disease remains obscure. However, it is not a fungus, bacterium, nematode, or mite. It is probably a virus.

Under natural infection, the following varieties and lines of *O. sativa* were susceptible to ragged stunt: BG34-8, BG90-2, BG374-2, BKN6986-108-2, Gow Ruang 88, IR8, IR20, IR22, IR24, IR26, IR29, IR30, IR3839-1, IR4427-115-3-3-3-3, IR4547-16-3-7, IR4568-586-2-2, IR4625-169-3-3-3, IR4723-345-1-3-1, IR4744-32-1-3-3, KN-IB-461-8-6-9-2, Pelita I/1, and TN1. *O. latifolia* can also be infected.

Since the infection has been noted in rice seedbeds, protecting seedlings and plants during early growth would probably reduce the disease incidence.

Study indicates viral nature of rice ragged stunt disease

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Dip preparations and ultrathin sections of plants naturally infected with ragged stunt disease at the IRRI farm and artificially inoculated by viruliferous *Nilaparvata lugens* were studied with an electron microscope at Hokkaido University. Electron micrographs showed

Electron micrographs show virus particles in dip preparation (top) and in a phloem cell of an ultrathin section (bottom) of a rice plant infected with ragged stunt disease.

polyhedral particles of 50–70 nm. The particles appeared abundantly in phloem cells (see photo), and in cells of the vein-swollings, or galls.

Although the determination of the infectivity of the particles is still under way, the electron micrographs serve as additional evidence that the causal agent of rice ragged stunt disease is a virus.

Resistance to bacterial leaf streak in India

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Bacterial leaf streak, caused by *Xanthomonas translucens*, is sometimes widespread and damaging, causing losses comparable with those from bacterial blight; however, little has been done on the development of resistant varieties. Varieties have been screened by artificial inoculation under natural conditions at Pantnagar since 1973. These results are from kharif 1973 and 1975, when disease pressure was heavy.

Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted in a puddled field with four checks: IR22 (resistant), Krisna (moderately resistant), IR8 (susceptible), and Cauvery (highly susceptible). The entries were inoculated at 45 days after sowing by rubbing bacterial suspension in cotton wool on the undersurface of the leaves. A spray inoculation increased disease pressure. Observations were recorded at the maximum-tillering stage and at 14 days after flowering on a scale of 1–9 (see table).

The following entries were recorded as resistant or moderately resistant to bacterial leaf streak:

KHARIF 1973

Resistant – SMI-6, RP 633, RP 189-2, OR 10-58, and OR 10-237.

Moderately resistant – IR579-119-2-3, CR 10R-157, ARC 5983, entries no. 6328, 6333, 6334, 6335, and 6336, RP 291-20, and RP4-13.

KHARIF 1975

Resistant – AD 1140, Hoyaku/Kolumba 540-1, Jikoku/Kolumba 540-5, Jikoku/Kolumba 540-6, Jikoku/Kolumba 540-7, Shiranui/Goinchiew 35-4, FH 487, MR 249, RP 1017-334-3-6,

Lines (no.) and their reactions to bacterial leaf streak during 1973 and 1975 kharif, Pantnagar, India.

Reaction	Lines (no.) from		
	AICRIP		IRRI ^a
	1973	1975	
Resistant	5	32	38
Moderately resistant	10	22	22
Moderately susceptible	22	64	21
Susceptible	25	933	252
Highly susceptible	23	230	7
Total	85	1281	340

^aInternational Rice Observational Nursery.

RP 975-145-3-3, RP 572-9-2-1, RP 572-9-5-1, RP 633-367-1-2, RP 633-385-2-7, RP 2001-25-1, RP 2003-1-2-5, RP 2004-1-6-3, RP 2007- CRHP-1, R 32-2617, R 27-2546, RJR 107-305, 2-25 (upland paddy x BR 4-10), 24-7-3 (SR 3-9 x TN1), R 7-2-3-1, R 7-3-1-1, R 8-12-1-1, R 19-1-1-1, R 106-2-1-3-2, IR2071-557-6-4, IR2071-588-1-1-1, IR2071-875-2-3-4, IR2071-636-5-2-6, BR 3-12-B-15-40, BR 51-67-1/CI, BR 51-74-2, BR 44-11-1, BR 51-99-1, BR 51-243-1, BR 51-319-9, BR 52-8-1, B 459b-Pu-4-5-6-5, IR2031-238-4-2-2-3, IR2035-290-2-3-1, Purple check (15/IR1103-1), IR2070-210-3-3-4, IR2588-19-1-1, IR2681-34-5-6, IR2871-53-2, IR3264-13-158-2-935-3, IR3265-138-2-5, BG 11-11, Chianung-Seu Yu 8, SRR 6726-76-2-3, BIC-Md-3-3, IR2031-724-2-3-4, IR2071-636-5-5, IR2070-423-2-5-6, IR2035-290-2-1-3, IR2848-26-1, IR944-102-2-3-2, TN1, IR1539-823-1-4, IR26, IR5492-3-147 (Glb₂), IR1820-52-24-1, IR2070-24-1-4-5, and JPS.

Moderately resistant — CR 139-1058, RP 633-590-3-1-1-1, RP 632-94-1-2-1-1, RP 744-104-76-1, RP 744-104-76, UPR 4 D-25-2,45457 (TN1/Co 29) x Hansa, HPNS 32, TR 14, RP 633-308-1-2, RP 938-31-4-6, RP 2001-9-1, R 102-2609, R 106-2567, R 111-2583, R 32-2615, R 22-2522, 12-2 (TN1/BR4-10), 11-2 (TN1/BR 4-10), BR 1-2B-40-3, BR 43-1-1-2, BR 51-46-5, BR 51-49-6, 31-14 (upland paddy x BR 4-10), R 1-1-1-1, IR2070-414-3-9, BR 51-114-2, BR 51-331-4, Giza 172, B 1896-52-8-3-1,

B441b-126-2-3-1, IR1544-181-1-1, IR2035-255-2-3-1, IR2063-65-2-1, IR2063-152-3-2, IR2063-185-2-2, IR2070-834-1-2, IR2153-550-2-6, IR2786-120-1, IR2843-26-3, IR2071-625-1-252, IR2070-743-6-3-2, SPR 6726-134-2-26, IR1545-339-2-2, and RP 633-200-1-7-4-1.

Methods to artificially inoculate and screen rice varieties for resistance to stem rot disease under field conditions

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Two methods of inoculation for stem rot were tested during 1975–76: 1) placing a mycelial mass on potato-dextrose-agar among the injured culms of the hills, and 2) placing inoculum from autoclaved rice grains in the hills and tying the hills as in the International Rice Sheath Blight Nursery (IRSHBN). Ten hills each of 104 varieties were inoculated; at grain maturity, the inoculated hills were cut at the base for evaluation. The rotten tillers were counted by pressing between the fingers. Thirty-two varieties and lines showed less than 30% culm rotting and were rated as resistant. The rices that showed less than 20% culm infection included IR32, IR1529-680-3-2, IR2053-87-3-1, IR2061-214-3-3-28, IR2061-214-3-3-32,

Two methods of artificial inoculation for stem rot disease. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute.

Cultivar	Rotten tillers (%)		
	Mycelial mass	Grain inoculum	Av.
Chitraj	15	25	20
IR1817-2-143-3	20	25	23
IR944-85-1-2-1-1	21	23	22
IR910-12-3-1-1	9	36	23
BR9-17-6-4	12	29	21
BR13-231-1	25	31	28
IR579-80-1-2-1	27	31	29
IR20	25	38	32
IR781-177-3-2-2	28	39	34
Mukti	27	43	35
Kataktara	31	43	37
BR9-17-4-2	19	54	37
IR836-1-1-1	29	49	39
BR43-11-2	35	45	40
IR8	25	81	53
Chandina H/R 29-3	36	75	56

and Mahsuri (Improved). The IRSHBN method of placing grain inoculum was more effective than the other as shown by the higher percentage of infection in 16 varieties (see table).

Sources of resistance to ufra disease of rice in Bangladesh

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Eight species of wild rice and one cultivar were screened for resistance to ufra disease in the field and in pots. The wild rice species were *Oryza glaberrima*, *O. nivara*, *O. officinalis*, *O. perennis*, *O. rufipogon*, *O. sativa* var. *patua*, *O. spontanea*, and *O. subulata*. The *O. sativa* cultivar was R16-06. All plants were inoculated at the vegetative stage by introducing into the leaf sheath cavities about 1 ml of nematode suspension (approx. 1,000 *D. angustus*/ml) with a fine glass dropper. The inoculated potted plants were covered with polyethylene bags for 2 days to maintain proper humidity.

All the rices, except the wild species *O. subulata* and the cultivar R16-06, showed symptoms of ufra infection. *O. subulata* could not be infected at all. Although infection began on inoculated R16-06, the disease did not fully develop and no nematodes could be isolated from the plants at the mature stage. R16-06 is a deep-water rice that is sensitive to photoperiod, but its yield potential is low. *O. subulata* is a stiff-leaved rice. These two rices can be used as sources of resistance in future breeding programs for deep-water rice.

Rice disease survey: 1975

Summarized by H. E. Kauffman, joint coordinator and plant pathologist; T. Ebron, senior research assistant; and S. Merca, research assistant, International Rice Testing Program, IRRI

Scientists responded well to disease survey questionnaires sent out with the Rice Pathology Newsletter in late 1975. As in previous years, blast was the most widespread disease during 1975. It was